

Assessment and evaluation of knowledge, skills, and attitudes among pharmacy students: A comparative study between virtual and full face-to-face hospital internship program

Shalom James B. Apura¹, Anthony R. Marin¹, Emmanuel Ian Lorenz T. Pacao¹,

Edward Niño John M. Simeon^{1,2}, Jenica Marie J. Villanueva¹

¹Pharmacy Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

²Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Santo Tomas, España, Manila, Philippines

*Corresponding Author: sjbapura@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Internship or experiential education is the best period for acquiring knowledge and skills in hospital pharmacy to become a successful allied healthcare professional. The effectiveness of internship pharmacy internships is less assessed in the Philippines. However, assessing the student's clinical skills during the internship is crucial to ensure that the obtained competencies are practiced. This study aims to assess pharmacy students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes between virtual and face-to-face hospital pharmacy internships in the Philippines. It intends to evaluate the current status and condition of the hospital pharmacy internship setting and to determine the student's level of participation in various internship activities associated with the learning outcomes from the hospital pharmacy internship. The study utilized a descriptive, comparative design and self-administered questionnaire as a method of data collection. Based on the study's findings, there is a significant limitation observed between the knowledge, skills, and attitude of BS Pharmacy students who completed their hospital pharmacy internship virtually compared to the in-person internship program.

Keywords: Attitude; Experiential pharmacy practice; Hospital pharmacy; Internship; Knowledge; Learning outcomes; Skills.

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Introduction

Internships are supervised and structured learning opportunities in the industry, meaning that they provide students with actual work experience in their chosen field. Internships allow students to explore and advance their careers while gaining new skills. Experiential Pharmacy Practice (EPP) is a requirement of the Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy curriculum (De Vera, 2021b) and requires internships in hospitals, manufacturing, community, public health and regulatory agencies, and institutional settings (Akel et al., 2021). Consequently, students wishing to participate in a hospital pharmacy internship must complete 300 hours in a CHED-accredited pharmacy institution (Licuanan, 2017).

Hospital pharmacy allows students to learn and practice through hospital practice training. The partner hospital institutions provide students with the core pharmacy management and pharmaceutical care services skills and expertise they need to function effectively as team members in an integrated healthcare system (Department of Health, 2019). In addition, it increases students' understanding of the pharmacist's role as an effective and efficient partner in delivering healthcare services (Khaira et al., 2020). Finally, it allows students to gain clinical experience, strengthen their professional judgment, and increase self-assurance when conversing with patients and physicians (Liao et al., 2021).

The pandemic has made it challenging to implement internship programs and has recently restricted face-to-face training (Bugis, 2020). In response, the CHED COVID-19 advisory advised higher education institutions to exercise flexibility to adjust, modify, and reduce requirements with as much regard as possible for the students (De Vera & Duque, 2021). In the last academic years, face-to-face internship programs have replaced virtual internships since the BS Pharmacy degree requires experiential pharmacy practice in numerous practice areas such as hospitals (Almohammed et al., 2021; Lyons et al., 2020). This transition has led to varied experiences and perceptions among students (Malhotra et al., 2022). The management of these internships during the pandemic has been a critical focus for educators (Hsu et al., 2021).

This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of BS Pharmacy students from St. Dominic College of Asia in Bacoor, the Philippines, who participated in virtual compared to the full face-to-face internship program, adding to the body of knowledge on student experiences during this unique period (Cernasev et al., 2021; Choo & Rahim, 2021).

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

The research utilized a relevant descriptive and comparative approach to obtain the information required for this study. Descriptive research was conducted using online survey questionnaires administered through Google forms best to address the questions, statements, and objectives. The researchers chose this approach since it enabled them to assess the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of BS Pharmacy students who complete their internship virtually, as opposed to face-to-face hospital internship programs.

Study Population

The study sample consists of fourth-year pharmacy students from institutions accredited by the Philippine Association of Colleges of Pharmacy (PACOP) who enrolled in virtual or full-face-to-face hospital internship programs between 2020 and 2022. Given the limited number of available respondents, the study employed non-probability sampling based on purposive sampling. In other words, the sample population in this technique is selected "on purpose." All responders voluntarily participated and signed informed consent forms.

Inclusion Criteria

All fourth-year Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy program students who have completed either a virtual or full-face-to-face internship possess a certificate of completion in hospital pharmacy internship between 2020 to 2022 and are willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

All first- to third-year BS Pharmacy students were excluded from the study because they had not yet done with their pharmacy practice experience or hospital pharmacy internship.

Data Collection

A validated survey questionnaire based on a prior study by Carrido et al. (2015) was utilized to obtain the data. Based on a five-point Likert scale question, it assessed the respondent's level of agreement with each of the specified learning outcomes the student was anticipated to obtain after completing their hospital internship (5 = strongly agree and 1 = strongly disagree). The knowledge and skill questions were based on the core competencies outlined in the PACOP Internship Manual. In contrast, the attitude questions were adapted from the Student-Service Learning Survey used by Jackel to evaluate the effectiveness of internship programs and were adapted to the hospital pharmacy internship program. The instrument employed true/false and dichotomous questions for the first and last sections, respectively. For dichotomous questions, the Yes and No responses were counted and divided by the total number of participants to determine the percentages of Yes and No for each question. For the multiple-choice portion of the question, the researcher employed the point scale provided in the following table.

Statistical Analysis

The collected research data was processed and encoded in Microsoft Excel. Researchers used descriptive statistics to describe data using frequency tables and pie charts. The various study variables were evaluated using descriptive statistics to measure the frequency, mean, and standard deviation.

Results and Discussion

Demographics

One hundred (100) students from various PACOP-accredited institutions participated in this study. For the demographic profile, an equal number of respondents enrolled in virtual and full face-to-face hospital internship programs (50.0%; n=50). St. Dominic Medical Center hosted the majority (30%, n=15) of the hospital training establishment's interns for the virtual internship program. While the majority, 46% (n=23), completed their entire hospital internship at Makati Medical Center. The majority were females (74%; n=74), with the age being 23 (34%; n=34).

Level of Participation in Hospital Pharmacy Internship Activities

Table 1 demonstrates the extent to which students participated in virtual (A) and face-to-face (B) hospital pharmacy internships. One hundred percent (100%) of students who completed a face-to-face internship participated in their orientation on hospital policies and procedures, pharmacy tours, and pharmaceutical storage requirements. As the host-training establishment commonly did pharmaceutical compounding, assisting in compounding was the least participated by virtual internship category, with 60% (n=3) of participants agreeing. In contrast, 50% (n=25) of students who experienced the entire face-to-face experience were least involved in the pricing of pharmaceutical products.

Table 1. Level of Participation in Hospital Pharmacy Internship Activities (n=50)

Activities in Hospital Pharmacy Internship		Category	Frequency	% YES	SD
1.	Were HTE able to provide an orientation on the policies and procedures of their hospital?	A	48	96%	0.20
		B	50	100%	0.00
2.	Were you given a hospital tour (where pharmacy services are involved)?	A	16	32%	0.47
		B	50	100%	0.00
3.	Were you able to perform prescription reading and interpretation?	A	42	84%	0.37
		B	48	96%	0.20
4.	Have you managed to assist in filling prescription orders?	A	9	18%	0.39
		B	43	86%	0.35
5.	Have you recorded prescription in prescription record book?	A	11	22%	0.42
		B	47	94%	0.24
6.	Have you experienced being involved in the pricing of drug products?	A	9	18%	0.39
		B	25	50%	0.51
7.	Were you able to repack and label the drugs under the supervision of a pharmacist?	A	7	14%	0.35
		B	41	82%	0.39
8.	Are you capable of performing an inventory of the drugs?	A	8	16%	0.37
		B	44	88%	0.33
9.	Were you able to have yourself acquainted with the information about drugs on therapeutic classification and use, dosage forms, generic/brand name, drug classification, manufacturer, and mode of transmission?	A	46	92%	0.27
		B	48	96%	0.20
10.	Were you able to assist in dispensing drugs?	A	8	16%	0.37
		B	47	94%	0.24
11.	Were you capable of providing drug information to queries from patients, with validation by the preceptor?	A	41	82%	0.39
		B	37	74%	0.44
12.	Were you able to familiarize yourself with the storage requirement of the drugs?	A	42	84%	0.37
		B	48	96%	0.20
13.	Have you experienced communicating with the patients?	A	31	62%	0.49
		B	45	90%	0.30
14.	Are you familiarizing yourself with the procedure in drug procurement?	A	38	76%	0.43
		B	45	90%	0.30
15.	Were you able to acquire knowledge of accounting procurement?	A	28	56%	0.50
		B	28	56%	0.50
16.	Have you replenished the drugs on the shelves?	A	6	12%	0.33
		B	47	94%	0.24
17.	Were you able to receive an orientation in placing orders and purchases?	A	17	34%	0.48
		B	39	78%	0.42
18.	Have you experienced assisting in compounding?	A	3	6%	0.24
		B	27	54%	0.50
19.	Were you able to make paper tablets?	A	7	14%	0.35
		B	30	60%	0.49
20.	Were you able to check drug expiration?	A	12	24%	0.43
		B	48	96%	0.20
21.	Have you managed to identify and document adverse drug reactions from actual cases provided by the preceptor?	A	39	78%	0.42
		B	32	64%	0.48
22.	Were you able to perform a medication history interview with the preceptor's supervision?	A	34	68%	0.47
		B	32	64%	0.48
23.	Were you able to observe HTE with workload and productivity management?	A	27	54%	0.50
		B	47	94%	0.24
24.	Does the HTE conduct control of drug expenditures?	A	18	36%	0.48
		B	41	82%	0.39
25.	Does the pharmacist preceptor provide pharmaceutical expertise in evaluating drugs for possible inclusion in the hospital formulary?	A	45	90%	0.30
		B	46	92%	0.27

26. Were you able to demonstrate skills in medication review and reconciliation skills?	A	38	76%	0.43
	B	34	68%	0.47
27. Were you able to perform unit dose dispensing UDSS in the HTE?	A	8	16%	0.37
	B	32	64%	0.48
28. Have you received an orientation in processing the returns policy, e.g., pharmacy to the supplier?	A	30	60%	0.49
	B	41	82%	0.39
29. Were you taught to consider the different categories and specific storage requirements?	A	44	88%	0.33
	B	47	94%	0.24
30. Were you able to communicate effectively with pharmacists, doctors, nurses, other healthcare providers, and the patient?	A	35	70%	0.46
	B	49	98%	0.14

Legend: A – virtual internship; B – Full face-to-face internship

Assessing the Students' Knowledge in the Participation of Hospital Pharmacy Internships

Table 2. Assessment of the Students' Knowledge in Hospital Pharmacy Internships (n=50)

	Statements	Category	Frequency	% YES	SD
1.	The generic name of Dalacin C is Clindamycin.	A	49	98%	0.14
		B	50	100%	0.00
2.	Unit dose dispensing or distribution system is a system wherein the pharmacy prepares the medication for a patient for 24 hours.	A	47	94%	0.24
		B	49	98%	0.14
3.	Non-charge floor stock system includes the medications placed in the nursing station used by all the patients on the floor.	A	43	86%	0.35
		B	47	94%	0.24
4.	Formulary systems are drugs approved for use within the hospital or health system.	A	48	96%	0.20
		B	49	98%	0.14
5.	Lactated Ringer's (LR) has a similar electrolyte content with serum but does not contain magnesium, and it has potassium; therefore, it is not used in patients with renal failure as it can cause hyperkalemia.	A	40	80%	0.40
		B	42	84%	0.37
6.	Individual prescription system is a system wherein drugs are readily available in the nursing units.	A	20	40%	0.49
		B	37	74%	0.44
7.	The system arrangement of the medicines in a pharmacy is based on therapeutic category, alphabetically by generic name or by dosage forms.	A	47	94%	0.24
		B	47	94%	0.24
8.	Of all three medication errors, violative error is the only error to be filled and reported to the nearest DOH branch.	A	28	56%	0.50
		B	41	82%	0.39
9.	Under the types of ADRs, Type E (Idiosyncrasy) is a reaction linked and determined through the individual's genes.	A	13	26%	0.44
		B	31	62%	0.49
10.	Based on the R.A. 6675: Generic Act of 1988, we have three prescription error types: Erroneous, Violative, and Impossible.	A	48	96%	0.20
		B	46	92%	0.27
11.	The creation of AO NO. 50-A S. 2001 led to the establishment of DOH Botika in the DOH retained Hospital.	A	11	22%	0.42
		B	37	74%	0.44
12.	Hospitals should adhere to the principles of transparency, accountability, and price competitiveness and should adequately monitor the prices of medicines as specified in RA 9184.	A	48	96%	0.20
		B	49	98%	0.14
13.	Pharmaceutical care provides medication therapy to attain measurable outcomes that enhance the patient's quality of life.	A	50	100%	0.00
		B	48	96%	0.20

14. I gtt ou bid x 7d translates; Instill one drop to both eyes once daily for seven days.	A	32	64%	0.48
	B	39	78%	0.42
15. Pre-signing black prescriptions for any purpose is PROHIBITED.	A	49	98%	0.14
	B	50	100%	0.00

Legend: A – virtual internship; B – Full face-to-face internship

Table 2 summarizes the responses about the respondent's level of knowledge after completing the hospital pharmacy internship program. Students who participated in face-to-face internships were more knowledgeable than those who participated in virtual internships. According to the results, Category B answered most questions correctly except for questions 10 and 13. On the basis of the data, virtual internships met most of the theoretical claims. This is corroborated by the research of Soffer and Nachmias (2018), which indicates that respondents gain from studying and learning a particular topic from home, as online learning offers greater flexibility and convenience than face-to-face instruction.

Assessing Students' Skills in Hospital Pharmacy Internships

Table 3. Assessment of the Students' Skills in Hospital Pharmacy Internships (n=50)

Statements	Category	Frequency	% YES	SD
1. Have you had the opportunity to remove medications from bulk containers, fill smaller containers, and create and apply labels?	A	7	14%	0.35
	B	41	82%	0.39
2. Were you able to arrange the stocks in the hospital pharmacy?	A	8	16%	0.37
	B	50	100%	0
3. Have you chosen an appropriate location for storing medications, such as poisons, flammables, perishables, and regulated substances?	A	39	78%	0.42
	B	42	84%	0.37
4. Have you been able to rotate supplies to ensure their freshness, determine acceptable stock levels, and order supplies?	A	8	16%	0.37
	B	49	98%	0.14
5. Are you capable of processing, filling, and/or dispensing prescriptions?	A	13	26%	0.44
	B	45	90%	0.30
6. Were you able to experience labeling loose tablets?	A	10	20%	0.40
	B	44	88%	0.33
7. Have you managed to process returns in the hospital pharmacy?	A	8	16%	0.37
	B	33	66%	0.48
8. Were you able to perform record-keeping, accounting, and reporting systems?	A	19	38%	0.49
	B	38	76%	0.43
9. Have you practiced verbal communication with colleagues, healthcare professionals, and staff?	A	36	72%	0.45
	B	47	94%	0.24
10. Were you able to provide drug information?	A	47	94%	0.24
	B	41	82%	0.39
11. Were you able to identify medication order/prescription errors correctly and quickly?	A	46	92%	0.27
	B	43	86%	0.35
12. Have you managed to provide patient counseling?	A	42	84%	0.37
	B	33	66%	0.48

Legend: A – virtual internship; B – Full face-to-face internship

Table 3 shows the summary of responses based on the skills gained by the students after completing the hospital pharmacy internship program. Students who participated in a virtual internship were more involved in providing pharmacological information (94%), identifying pharmaceutical order/prescription problems correctly and promptly (92%), and providing patient counseling (84%). This can be due to the growth and popularity of tele-pharmacy in the country. According to the study conducted by Plantado et al. (2021), the transition to the “new normal” necessitates the deployment of alternative

platforms to enhance existing health information sources. An online tele-pharmacy service may be utilized as a part of primary care to provide and clarify pharmaceutical information. In contrast, according to McDermott's (1995) study, health education and patient counseling are the most important activities for hospital interns to be taught and learn; however, the results of the study revealed that sixty-six percent (66%) of the full face-to-face had not provided patient counseling. According to Bormuth et al. (2021), it is reasonable that hospital or medical interns, in general, are not permitted to do actual patient counseling. In contrast to those who participate in a virtual internship, students who participate in a full face-to-face internship were able to personally experience the other competencies listed in the survey at their host training institution, making them more prepared for future careers.

Assessing the Students' Attitude in Hospital Pharmacy Internships

Table 4 summarizes the response based on the students' acquired attitude after completing the hospital pharmacy internship program. Students who participate in a face-to-face internship score higher on attitude assessments than those who participate in a virtual internship, although the mean scores were closely related.

Table 4. Assessment of the Students' Attitude in Hospital Pharmacy Internships (n=50)

Statements	Category	Mean	SD
1. When speaking with people, I am now more considerate and polite.	A	4.28	0.70
	B	4.78	0.58
2. I have gained the capacity to be more productive.	A	4.18	0.63
	B	4.58	0.64
3. I have a sense of satisfaction in doing something worthwhile.	A	4.28	0.64
	B	4.60	0.67
4. I understand and appreciate people with diverse backgrounds.	A	4.20	0.73
	B	4.64	0.63
5. I have a real, clear picture of what kind of person I am.	A	4.02	0.82
	B	4.52	0.65
6. It allowed me to make many new acquaintances, broadened my perspective, and made me feel that my efforts were worthwhile.	A	4.00	0.70
	B	4.54	0.65
7. This program boosted my tolerance and patience for task and work management.	A	4.08	0.63
	B	4.60	0.64
8. It helped me to reflect on my career planning.	A	4.14	0.64
	B	4.58	0.64
9. This changed my work values positively.	A	4.14	0.64
	B	4.66	0.63
10. I learned to prioritize, remain professional and remember patient-care safety above all	A	4.24	0.74
	B	4.60	0.64
11. I become more dedicated to improving my profession.	A	4.20	0.70
	B	4.52	0.68
12. I learned to adapt to ever-changing situations and practice environments.	A	4.18	0.69
	B	4.58	0.67
13. I recognize my professional personal strengths and weaknesses.	A	4.16	0.65
	B	4.58	0.64
14. I enhance my capacity for independent work and learning.	A	4.20	0.64
	B	4.56	0.67
15. I show compassion or concern towards my customers or patients.	A	4.18	0.69
	B	4.64	0.63
16. I develop initiative through my internship training in the community.	A	4.22	0.71
	B	4.50	0.81
17. I desire even more to pursue my pharmacy degree.	A	4.16	0.74
	B	4.68	0.62

18. I collaborate effectively with peers, other health care professionals, and patients to optimize patient care.	A	4.14	0.70
	B	4.56	0.64
19. I am increasing my ability to become a leader.	A	4.10	0.76
	B	4.56	0.70
20. I strongly adhere to the national and international pharmacist code of ethics.	A	4.12	0.80
	B	4.62	0.64

Legend: A – virtual internship; B – Full face-to-face internship

When it comes to being more considerate and polite when speaking with others, students who complete a full face-to-face internship score the highest. This may result from constant involvement with their workplace instead of virtual internships. In addition, students who participated in a virtual internship scored lowest in making numerous friends, expanding their perspectives, and feeling that their efforts were worthwhile. Considering that they were required to stay at home for their internship, they had less interaction with their peers.

Evaluation of Achieved Learning Outcomes

Table 5. Evaluation of Achieved Learning Outcomes

Statements	Category	Mean	SD
1. Introduce students to the administrative and professional responsibilities of a hospital pharmacist.	A	4.38	0.67
	B	4.74	0.53
2. Provide pharmacy interns with the opportunity to obtain clinical experience, develop professional judgment, and grow confidence in their ability to communicate with patients and physicians.	A	4.18	0.63
	B	4.58	0.57
3. Given the institution’s demands, internalize the hospital pharmacist’s duties and obligations.	A	4.14	0.67
	B	4.64	0.63
4. Describe the distributive (basic hospital pharmacy area operations) and clinical pharmacy functions of the pharmacist.	A	4.12	0.72
	B	4.34	0.89
5. Apply the knowledge and skills gained from formal courses to actual dynamic patient care situations, such as but not limited to medication history taking, drug information provision, and documentation of adverse drug reactions.	A	4.02	0.65
	B	4.40	0.76
6. Undertake pharmacy calculations in practice.	A	4.10	0.74
	B	3.90	1.28
7. This program enhanced my tolerance and patience for tasks and work management.	A	4.14	0.73
	B	4.56	0.58
8. Develop an understanding of pharmacy procedures and recordkeeping.	A	4.22	0.62
	B	4.64	0.56
9. Demonstrate appropriate professional behaviors and communication skills.	A	4.24	0.62
	B	4.46	0.58
10. Recognize the significance of evidence-based practice in the treatment of individual patients.	A	4.16	0.62
	B	4.40	0.70
11. Incorporating knowledge of pathophysiology, pharmacology, and therapeutics into the development of pharmaceutical care programs.	A	4.10	0.74
	B	4.26	0.90
12. Understand the application of clinical and pharmacological skills in patient care.	A	4.10	0.71
	B	4.56	0.61
13. Evaluate information critically to support and defend the logical selection of medications for particular patients.	A	4.10	0.71
	B	4.50	0.58

Legend: A – virtual internship; B – Full face-to-face internship

Table 5 shows the evaluation of achieved learning outcomes. After completing the hospital pharmacy internship program, students were asked to evaluate the learning outcomes they had attained. Students who participated in a face-to-face internship scored higher on every criterion except performing

pharmaceutical calculations in practice, averaging only 3.90. On the other hand, they scored highest in familiarizing themselves with hospital pharmacists' professional and administrative functions. This may be attributed to the fact that they could observe their working environment, unlike those who participated in virtual internships, which limited their capacity to perform certain tasks.

Discussion

From the results shown, it can be seen that the Pharmacy student interns who conducted the hospital pharmacy internship online and in-person were able to follow their institution's objectives before the deployment of its students in their host-training establishment, in this case, in hospital pharmacies, proposed minimum curriculum requirements of Commission on Higher Education (CHED) (De Vera, 2021a) as well as the guidelines stated in the Hospital Pharmacy Management Manual of the Department of Health (Department of Health, 2019).

The points taken from their Hospital Pharmacy subject in their third year of college may have affected the outcomes of the internship program in terms of assessing these students in regard to knowledge and skills. For example, students who were able to conduct the internship program in person revealed that they have much more experience in dispensing activities within the hospital where the interns have most participated. They have also performed a minimal degree of patient interaction and were still unable to perform patient counseling; if there is, the interns only get to observe the said activity from their pharmacy preceptors (Wallman et al., 2011). Students who conducted the activities in person may still have limited prior knowledge of drugs and necessary skills and attitudes since it was their first deployed HTE program (Carrido et al., 2015). Unlike the interns from the online hospital pharmacy, in which they have conducted their community pharmacy first before being deployed in the online pharmacy, they could still fill the knowledge and skills compared to the interns from in-person hospital pharmacy internships. Opportunities to participate in the activities listed in the first section of the survey questionnaire are essential for further understanding the practice of the pharmacy profession (Carrido et al., 2015).

Despite reports of a lack of interaction between students and patients, hospital pharmacy interns have expressed overall satisfaction with their internship experience (online and face-to-face) (Huang et al., 2022). In terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, there were substantial variations in the mean skill scores of online and face-to-face participants. Students have learned primarily about drug classification, dosage forms, therapeutic uses, frequency, and modes of administration, and they are familiar with the brand and generic names, as well as the manufacturer or distributor of pharmaceutical products, as a result of their participation in a dispensing internship (Carrido et al., 2016). On the other hand, interns from virtual internships could not fully apply their abilities and knowledge online (Hsia et al., 2021). Therefore, this could be a factor that hinders their view in terms of preparing for their early career due to having only completed the internship virtually (Altwaitjry et al., 2021).

Limitations

This research only included students who have already completed a 300-hour hospital internship program. No additional experiential pharmacy practice program settings, including community, manufacturing, institutional, regulatory, or public health, will be included in the study.

Conclusion

The study gives information on the qualities between virtual and in-person hospital pharmacy practice internships in the Philippines. Students generally felt that their internship program resulted in positive experiences, satisfaction, and learning outcomes. However, it is significant to highlight that most

of the students' learning results centered on conventional technical activities have been limited from their prior hospital pharmacy course material, such as dispensing and drug procurement operations. The internship program lacked training in providing pharmaceutical care to both groups of students—virtual and face-to-face—such as patient counseling, a recent trend in the pharmacy field.

A program for internships that involves students in activities connected to clinical practice and scientific learning is highly advised in light of the paradigm change in the pharmacy profession. Additionally, it is suggested that educational institutions and pharmacy organizations develop guidelines for the hospital pharmacy internship to ensure that all students have comparable learning opportunities. It is also encouraged that the internship program is evaluated on a regular basis so that institutions can enhance and modify their respective programs to better prepare students for the demands of the pharmacy profession.

Since pharmacy currently serves as a professional health practice, educational curricula should emphasize the link between theoretical knowledge and actual practice in hospital pharmacies by involving students in more patient-centered and productive activities, such as significant levels of engagement in their host training institutions.

Conflicts of Interest

None.

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